

DISCONTINUOUSLY REINFORCED ALUMINUM COMPOSITE FOR LARGE STRUCTURAL TUBE APPLICATIONS

William C. Harrigan, Jr., J. F. Dolowy, Jr. and B. A. Webb
(DWA Composite Specialties, Inc. Chatsworth, California, USA)

ABSTRACT

Discontinuously reinforced aluminum composites possess isotropic properties that include; high specific stiffness, low thermal expansion, high thermal conductivity, high wear resistance and high strength. Combinations of these properties makes this family of composite materials ideal candidates for a variety of applications. Aerospace, aircraft and space structures benefit from the high mechanical properties and the low material density. Applications in automobile engines include pistons, piston pins, cam followers, connecting rods and push rods. Pistons have been made and tested in drag racing motorcycles and in "Grand American" automobiles. These composite have been designed and built for structural elements in sailing boats. The main structural beams were designed and built for the racing catamaran "Stars and Stripes '88". The property combinations and design considerations for this main beam application will be discussed in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

In May 1988 DWA Composite Specialties, Inc. was approached by the syndicate "Sail America" to build replacement beams for the catamaran "Stars and Stripes '88". The beams were made from aluminum and were 30.5 cm (12 inches) outside diameter with a wall thickness of 6.35mm (0.25 inch). The total length of the tubes was 9.2 meters (thirty feet). These beams were the main structure of the catamaran, Figure 1. The reason for making replacement tubes was to save structural weight. The catamaran was being built to defend the "America's Cup" against the challenge from the New Zeland Syndicate headed by Michael Faye. Actually two catamarans were being built, one had the "hard" sail and the other one had a conventional soft sail. The speed of a catamaran is determined by the weight of the structure and crew in light winds. At the time this project was started, neither catamaran was completed and the performance of the crafts was speculation at the time. The ability to save weight was very important in order to insure optimum performance of the boats.

When we started the project, we had 10 weeks to complete the tubes. The final tubes were calculated to weigh 148 Kg (325 pounds). The tubes were sized by the stiffness of the material of construction. The stiffness had to be isotropic since the tubes would react not only the mast loads but also the bending and torque loads caused by the raising of the one pontoon from the water during racing, Figure 2. We chose to produce the tubes from 20 v% SIC / 6061 Al composite because this material has an isotropic modulus of 103 GPa (15

million psi) rather than the 68.9 GPa (10 million psi) for the existing aluminum tube. By resizing the wall thickness of the tubes because of the increased stiffness of the composite, weight savings of 20 percent were predicted. The largest extrusion that had been made with any metal matrix composite was 91 Kg (200 pounds). We therefore, had to make an extrusion billet that was twice as big as the largest we made in the past. This had to be done with no new tooling, since machining quotes were for 16 to 18 week delivery for tooling of this size. Our present tooling allowed us to produce a billet that weighed 190 Kg (420 pounds). The billet dimensions were 35.5 cm (14 inch) diameter and 71 cm (28 inches) long. Four of these billets were made and delivered before July 4, 1988.

The tubes had to be extruded using existing tooling since the long lead time existed for the extrusion tooling also. Tooling was found at Aluminum Company of America's Extrusion Facility in Lafayette, Indiana. The tooling would allow us to produce the tubes from an 46 cm (18 inch) diameter container. However, the billets had to be supplied with a 29.5 cm (11.625 inch) diameter hole in them, since this hole size was too large to be pierced by the press for which the tooling existed. We found that Curtiss Wright Extrusion Company in Buffalo, New York could pierce the billets by back extruding. Curtiss Wright needed to receive the starting billets with a maximum diameter of 43.8 cm (17.25 inches) and a minimum diameter of 43 cm (17.0 inches). We were able to convert the 35.6 cm (14 inch) diameter billets into 43.8 cm (17.25 inch) diameter billets by upset forging. This process had been used in the past to enlarge 15 cm (6 inch) and 20 cm (8 inch) diameter billets to 18 and 23 cm (7 and 9 inch) diameters. The present forging demanded that the outer portion of the billets expand by 23 percent. This demanded that the original billet have full density in order to be able to withstand the forging operation. The billets were reduced in height from 71 cm (28 inches) to 48 cm (19 inches) during the forging operation. A photograph of a standard 91 Kg (200 pound) billet and one of the forged 190 Kg (420 pound) billets is shown in figure 3.

The back extrusion was done on a 4,000 ton press and resulted in a billet that was 44.5 cm (17.50 inches) outside diameter, 29.5 cm (11.625 inch) inside diameter and 79 cm (31 inches) long. The process of back extrusion was completed by punching the ran nose piece through the bottom of the original billet in order to preserve the inner surface of the pierced billet. The removed bottoms were used for preliminary tensile verification tests for the composite. The data is contained in Table 1. These data confirmed that the elastic modulus of this composite was 103 GPa (15 million psi). The completed billets were shipped from Buffalo, New York to Lafayette, Indiana for final extrusion. The Alcoa Extrusion Facility extruded the tubes in a 4,000 ton press with an 46 cm (18 inch) container and an 29 cm (11.5 inch) mandrel. This tooling produces 30.5 cm (12.00 inch) diameter aluminum tubes with 6.35 mm (1/4 inch) walls. This facility had never extruded metal matrix composite prior to this project, and the first four billet they extruded had to be deliverable. The tubes were extruded to a length of 11 to 12 meters (36 to 39 feet) in order to allow the ends to be gripped for stretch straightening. The heat treatment and stretch straightening of the tubes was done at Alcoa Extrusion Facility in Lafayette, Indiana. These tubes were the first metal matrix composite heat treated by this facility. The tubes were solution treated in a 14 meter (45 foot) tall vertical furnace and quenched into water as if it were 6061 aluminum. The tubes were then stretched by gripping the

ends with plugs inserted into the tubes. They were stretched to a strain level of between 0.25 and 0.75 percent. This was done in order to preserve the tubes during the stretch operation. The tubes were then aged to a T-6 condition. Tubes 1 and 3 were chosen for final delivery. Tensile samples were taken from these tubes in the excess region between the stretch grip marks and the actual delivered length. These samples were tested without further heat treatment. The data from these tests are contained in Table 2. Tensile samples were also taken from the ends of tubes 2 and 4. These samples were heat treated to T-6 after machining. The data from these tests are also contained in Table 2. These data demonstrate that the tensile properties measured for samples heat treated after machining are the same as those measured for samples taken from the heat treated tubes.

The Tubes were shipped to Chem-Mill International in Rosamond, California. The tubes weighed the same as the aluminum tubes at this point and had to be chem-milled to reduce the wall thickness in order to achieve the weight savings. Calculations were made to determine the wall thickness necessary to match the stiffness of the aluminum tubes with the composite tubes. These calculations indicated that the tubes needed to be chem-milled to a wall thickness of 4.6 mm (0.180 inches). The tubes had many attachment points for the net floor, winches and the mast. These locations had to remain 6.35 mm (0.25 inches) thick for stability. The tubes therefore had to be masked in the thick regions during the chem-milling. A photograph of the forward tube being chem-milled appears in figure 4. The tubes had to be chem-milled in halves because the displacement of over 3200 Kg (7,000 pounds) of the fluid by the tubes was thought to be excessive for a single operation. The chem-milling operation reduced the weight of the forward tube to 134 Kg (295 pounds) and the after tube to 129 Kg (285 pounds) for weight savings of 15.4 and 18.9 percent.

The tubes were delivered on August 11, ten days after the original scheduled delivery date. The tubes were found to be 31 cm (12.25 inch) outside diameter with a wall thickness of 6.35 mm (0.250 inch) in the protected areas and 4.6 mm (0.180 inch) in the chem-milled areas. The greater diameter was caused by two factors, the composite has a lower expansion coefficient than aluminum and therefore shrunk less after extrusion and the composite was not stretched to the extent that the aluminum tubes are stretched. This combination of factors can be compensated for in future work when tooling can be designed and built. The tubes were "proof tested" by the "Stars and Stripes '88" crew by attaching the ends of the tube to pilings with ropes at 8 meter (26 foot) spacing. The center of the tube was loaded with a wire rope and a crane to a load of 3,910 Kg (8,600 pounds). The deflection of the tube was measured at various load levels and the modulus of 103 GPa (15 million psi) was demonstrated. The tubes were not installed on the soft sail catamaran due to the lack of time for the installation. This lack of time was a combination of the rework necessary to make up for the tube oversize and the large number of holes that had to be drilled and tapped for the installation of the net floor of the catamaran.

CONCLUSIONS

This program demonstrated that 20 v% SiC / 6061 Aluminum composite can be made into large structures such as the main beams for the catamaran "Stars and Stripes '88". These structures weighed 132 Kg (290 pounds) and saved approximately 19 percent of the weight of these tubes. These tubes were made on existing equipment with existing tooling in a time of 14 weeks. The structure that was made was proof tested and demonstrated that a structure of this size reacts as predicted.

Table 1

Tensile Properties of Billet End Pieces					
Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Yield Strength (MPa)	Ultimate Strength (MPa)	Strain at Failure (%)	Reduction In Area (%)	Hardness Rockwell (B)
Billet 1					
113.6	415.6	489.8	4.44	5.84	81
106.7	430.5	485.8	4.75	7.75	80
Billet 2					
109.2	425.6	485.1	4.27	6.01	76
106.1	421.6	485.0	4.08	3.76	76
Billet 3					
102.5	400.9	475.1	4.51	5.80	83
103.9	416.8	484.8	4.85	6.40	83
Billet 4					
107.7	416.4	485.9	4.07	5.21	84
104.1	413.1	481.6	5.09	7.52	83

Table 2

Tensile Data for Extruded Tubes					
Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Yield Strength (MPa)	Ultimate Strength (MPa)	Strain at Failure (%)	Reduction in Area (%)	Hardness Rockwell (B)
Tube 1					
106.1	384.5	434.6	3.21	7.10	76.5
107.0	408.9	462.2	3.77	7.29	78.5
106.7	399.4	446.0	3.08	8.66	78.0
Tube 2					
107.7	407.8	482.5	4.48	7.88	81.0
109.9	420.4	496.0	4.92	9.32	82.0
Tube 3					
110.4	405.0	529.1	5.85	9.12	83.5
104.6	408.8	479.8	5.06	8.72	83.0
105.6	405.2	479.1	5.69	10.37	82.0
111.5	411.8	486.3	4.95	8.64	81.0
Tube 4					
110.1	411.5	483.0	5.11	7.16	80.0
114.3	409.2	474.2	5.45	8.85	81.0

Figure 1 Photograph of location of main beams of catamaran

Figure 2 Photograph of "Stars and Stripes '88" racing on one hull

Figure 3 Photograph of 91 Kg (200 Lb) and 190 Kg (420 Lb) billets

Figure 4 Photograph of 10 Meter (33 ft) forward beam being chem-milled